

Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle

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D3.7 TESTED SHORT SDE STACK - Public

31.12.2024

WP3 - Materials and catalysts development

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Preface

HySelect will demonstrate the production of hydrogen (H₂) by splitting water via concentrated solar technologies (CST) with an attractive efficiency and cost, through the Hybrid Sulphur cycle (HyS). The HyS consists of two central steps: the high temperature -yet below-900°C -decomposition of sulphuric acid forming Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and the subsequent low temperature (50-80°C) SO₂ depolarized electrolysis (SDE) of water to produce H₂. HySelect will introduce, develop and operate under real conditions a complete H₂ production chain focusing on two innovative, full scale plant prototype core devices for both steps of the HyS cycle: an allothermally heated, spatially decoupled from a centrifugal particle solar receiver, sulphuric acid decomposition-Sulphur trioxide splitting (SAD-STs) reactor and a Sulphur dioxide depolarized electrolyzer (SDE) without expensive Platinum Group Metals (PGMs). Furthermore, a heat recovery system will be integrated to exploit the temperature difference within the cycle and boost the overall process efficiency. In the course of the work, non-critical materials and catalysts will be developed, qualified and integrated into the plant scale prototype units for both the acid splitting reactor and the SDE unit. Experimental work will be accompanied by component modelling and overall process simulation and culminate with a demonstration of the complete process integrating its key units of a 750kW_{th} centrifugal particle receiver, a hot particles storage system, a 250kW_{th} SAD-STs and a 100kW_e SDE into a pilot plant. Testing for a period of at least 6 months in a large-scale solar tower, driven with smart operation and control strategies, will establish the HySelect targeted efficiency and costs. Finally, an overall process evaluation will be carried out in order to assess the technical and economic prospects of the HySelect technology, directly linked to the know-how and developments of the sulphuric acid and water electrolyzers industries.

DLR	German Aerospace Center	DE	
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	GR	CERTH CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS
AALTO	Aalto University	FI	A! Aalto University
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	IT	
FENR	FEN Research GmbH	AT	
GRILLO	Grillo Werke AG	DE	

Summary

This document is Deliverable D3.7. Efforts to improve and test the SO₂ depolarized electrolyser (SDE) prototype were made at Aalto University. The aim was to enhance the current design of the SDE setup with better plate coatings, optimized membrane materials, and a refined configuration. Our plan involved integrating these improvements and conducting over 50 hours of rigorous testing to evaluate the performance of the five-cell stack. The deliverable aimed at validating the improvements and ensuring the prototype was ready for future applications. Significant improvements were made at systemic level that include changes in gas analysis system, optimization of catholyte flows, reduction in sulfuric acid concentration, etc.

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1. Introduction

Deliverable D3.7 Tested short SDE stack, is developed within WP3, Materials and catalysts development. The scope of D3.7 is to incorporate new materials from Tasks 3.3 and 3.4 and assemble and extensively test the stack at AALTO. The materials that have been explored will be documented in D3.5 and D3.6. The results from Tasks 3.3 and 3.4 were presented in the first periodic report. The experiments for the current deliverable have been implemented in a five-cell stack with the individual cell surface area of 100 cm² and tested for 50 hours.

Several improvements were made to the system along with the testing of new materials and components to optimize the overall system performance as well as prevent sulfur formation which is one of the major challenges in the SDE technology. A significantly smaller amount of sulfur was observed on the cathode side compared to the previous system as the catholyte was not recirculated. A quantitative gas analysis was achieved, which was previously unavailable and will significantly enhance the understanding the factors that influence the performance of the system, such as the SO₂ carry over in the cell, thus facilitating the understanding of the impact of the material improvements.

The new bipolar plates were equipped with the most advanced and durable coatings, and this material development will be discussed in separate deliverable D3.6. To prevent the SO₂ carry over, three different types of membranes were tested: Ceramhyd, Solvay Aquivion and Nafion™ 117. Among them, Nafion™ 117 was determined to be the best as will be demonstrated in D3.5. Overall, the stack experiments were planned with the most optimized materials that were available in large quantities that are required for bench scale experiments.

2. System Optimization

To control the SO₂ feed in a more accurate manner, a flow controller was incorporated in the anolyte feed to the anolyte tank. Previously, the SO₂ feed to the anolyte tank was carried out solely by using a gas bottle regulator that only provides the feed pressure. The use of regulator only resulted in higher fluctuation of the SO₂ feed in the tank and achieving the required concentration of SO₂ in the anolyte was extremely challenging.

The Gas-Liquid separator (GLS) used in the system was modified to accommodate the fact that the catholyte was not recirculated in the optimized cell. The previous system used a GLS that had Raschig rings in the filled in the first compartment that allowed separation of the gases from the electrolyte as shown in Fig. 1. This required high catholyte flow rates which meant that a lot of catholyte (in the range of 100s of liters) would be required to maintain the separation and flow within the GLS. The first compartment of the GLS was removed to decrease flow resistance allowing lower catholyte flow rates.

Significant improvements were made in the gas analysis system used in the SDE setup. In the older setup, water displacement method was used to determine the amount of gas produced during electrolysis, wherein the product gas was allowed to flow into a measuring cylinder filled with water, and volume of product gas was determined by the amount of water displaced. In the current setup, the incorporation of the flow meter and the corresponding software allows for continuous monitoring of gas production, improving the accuracy and simplicity of measurement via automation of the process.

Fig. 1 Comparison of the original (left) and improved (right) gas liquid separator.

3. Experimental procedure

The experiment utilized an Electro MP Cell, available in both single-cell and multi-cell configurations [1]. The cell was equipped with bipolar plates made of SS 904L stainless steel (Outotec), featuring a gold coating with a thickness of 100 nm and an active surface area of 100 cm². A commercial Nafion™ 117 membrane (Ion Power, Inc.) served as the proton exchange membrane (PEM), with dimensions of 10 cm x 10 cm. The electrolyte used in the setup was 5 wt% sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). The analysis equipment used to measure each of the parameters has been listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters Measured and Analysis Equipment

S.No.	Parameters measured	Equipment
1	Density measurement - H ₂ SO ₄ conc.	Pycnometer
2	Titration - SO ₂ concentration	Titroline 5000
3	Hydrogen produced	Bronkhorst low ΔP flow flow meter
4	Chronoamperometry	IviumStat.h, IviumBoost (40 A)
5	SO ₂ and H ₂ S sensor readings	Blackline Safety Gas Sensor

The experimental setup involved the assembly of an Electro MP Cell stack, which was prepared a day prior to the run. The assembly followed a specific sequence: end plate, bipolar plate, cathode flow field, membrane, anode flow field, bipolar plate, and end plate, with gaskets placed between each part. The cell was tightened using a torque wrench to 12 Nm and immersed in ultrapure water to prevent membrane drying. The stack consisted of five cells in a Z-configuration where the same, higher concentrated SO₂ feed is fed to all of the cells in the stack as shown in Fig. 2. This offers the highest SO₂ concentration for the whole active area of the cell.

Fig. 2 Schematic of Z-configuration for stack assembly

SO₂ concentrations in the electrolyte streams were measured using bichromatometry titration having 0.15 M Ammonium dichromate as the titration solution. The operations of bichromatometry titration are described in our previous work [2]. The titration was automated, detecting endpoints through potential changes, and performed every hour for multi-cell setups. Samples of 15 mL were analyzed immediately to prevent SO₂ loss, and the titrant volume was converted to SO₂ concentration using a specified correlation. Spent solutions were safely disposed of post-analysis.

Electrolyte density was monitored using a pycnometer. The pycnometer was weighed empty and then filled with 25 mL of electrolyte, and the density was calculated from the mass difference. The resulting density was used to determine the H₂SO₄ concentration via a conversion table or online calculator. Density measurements were conducted every two hours for the anolyte, while catholyte samples were settled overnight before measurement.

Gas production and composition were monitored throughout the experiment. A flow controller regulated gas flows, switching between N₂ and SO₂ using Bronkhorst Flowsuite software [3], while a flow meter recorded total gas production. Hourly readings from gas sensors provided H₂S and SO₂ concentrations. The hydrogen output was calculated by subtracting the measured H₂S and SO₂ volumes from the total gas volume.

Before operation, the anolyte tank was filled with prepared electrolyte using a recirculation bypass system. Catholyte was pumped from a separate can. After filling, the bypass was removed, and the inlet and outlet streams of the cells were reconnected to complete the setup.

Following electrolysis, the system was shut down systematically. Potentiostat and booster connections were removed, pumps were turned off, and the electrolyte streams were disconnected. The stack was dismantled, cleaned, or immersed in distilled water for storage. Spent catholyte was safely disposed of in drains due to low SO₂ concentration, while anolyte, with higher SO₂ levels, was sent for recycling. Titration and density analysis samples were also disposed of appropriately.

4. Results and discussion

The experiment was conducted over three days, following university safety guidelines, with work taking place from 7:00 AM to 12:00 PM each day. Prior to electrolysis, SO₂ was bubbled into the anolyte at a rate of 0.144 L/min for 10 hours to reach a concentration of 200 mM. All equipment was checked for leaks, and the stack was assembled with the membranes kept hydrated.

Electrolysis was performed at a constant potential of 8.5V for a period of 50 hours (Fig 3). The cylindrical design of the anolyte tank caused uneven mixing, so to achieve the same concentration of SO₂ throughout the tank, it took an hour of anolyte recirculation. This explains the variation in the SO₂ concentration that was eventually consumed leading to a drop in the current and further stabilization with passage of time. A lot of fluctuation can be seen in the current due to the accumulation of sulfur in the stack and the catholyte flow rate was increased to remove the sulfur. Pycnometer readings of catholyte density were affected by sulfur, so samples were decanted before measurements (Fig. 5). Due to the overnight pause, at the 18th hour, the catholyte pipes were flushed with 15 L of distilled water at a high flow rate (45 L/h) for 20 minutes. This was done to prevent any possible sulfur accumulation or additional SO₂ carryover even though the flushing couldn't completely remove all the sulfur.

Fig 3 Electrolysis at constant potential of 8.5 V for 50 hours

Fig. 4 SO₂ concentration in the anolyte and catholyte outlet stream during the 50-hour run

The current decreased steadily to 0.8 A at the end of 34 hours as the SO₂ in the anolyte was being consumed (as can be seen in the Fig. 4), after 34 hours the concentration in the anolyte tank was 55mM. As the electrolysis progressed, the catholyte was clearer, indicating progress

in sulfur removal. The catholyte pipes were flushed again at the 35th hour, but less sulfur was present this time. A stable current between 0.65–0.75 A was maintained between 35–50 hours. The SO₂ concentration in the anolyte stayed below 100 mM, which reduced crossover into the catholyte. Around 35th hour, the anolyte solution turned green, that can be a sign of corrosion issue on the gold-coated steel plate.

Fig. 5 H₂SO₄ concentration in the anolyte and catholyte outlet stream during the 50-hour run

After electrolysis, the cell was disassembled, and the bipolar plates were observed for sulfur deposition and corrosion of gold coating. It was observed that two of the anode plates were corroded and all the cathode plates had sulfur deposited on them. One of the anode plates had a scratch on it which was not observed during assembly while the other plate had corrosion of the gold coating itself which was most likely contributed by pitting corrosion starting from the sides of the plate.

Fig. 6 Total gas production for 50 hours in L/h along with purity of hydrogen in mol %

The 50-h run provided interesting new results as this long experiment has not been run before with non-pressurized SDE set-up and it revealed additional challenges when operated for longer periods of time. Fig 3 present the results of electrolysis of the 5-cell stack at constant potential of 8.5 V for 50 hours. Additionally, the gas analysis data (Fig. 6) with the purity of hydrogen in mol % has not been presented before. The purity measured using the data obtained from the gas sensor shows and provides a first look at the purity that can be expected for the produced hydrogen. The current behavior follows the trend of the amount of SO₂ available in the anolyte (Fig. 4) and subsequently the amount of H₂SO₄ that is formed at the anode (Fig. 5). In the electrolysis it was observed that the current and hydrogen produced decrease with the decrease in SO₂ concentration in the anolyte but also the amount of sulfur produced also reduced. This means that there is a tradeoff between SO₂ crossover and hydrogen production efficiency. At lower concentration of SO₂, it can be observed that the amount of solid sulfur is smaller, but at the cost of hydrogen produced and vice versa. The specific energy demand was calculated for the stack during the 50-h run and the average was found to be 150kWh of electricity/kg of hydrogen for our system (Fig. 7Fig. 7). This can be compared with the single cell run that was performed for three and a half hours and the average was 82.38 kWh of electricity/ kg of hydrogen (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7 Specific energy demand from 50-run in kWh of electricity per kg of hydrogen for stack.

Fig. 8 Specific energy demand in kWh of electricity per kg of hydrogen for single cell.

5. Conclusion

The requirements of the deliverable D3.7 was met, and further studies will be made to further improve the system for the long runs - for at least 100 hours as a part of WP 5. The performance of the 50h run provided important information related to the performance of the stack. The increase the accuracy and consistence of the SO₂ feed, flow controller needs to be troubleshooted and the inlet pressure for SO₂ flow controller must be optimized by addition of a pressure controller/sensor to prevent the phase change of SO₂ from gas to liquid. It is important to sediment and decant the catholyte outlet solution before pycnometry to reduces interference of Sulphur with the density readings. It is necessary to perform a surface analysis to each of the bipolar plates used in the cell to identify any possible scratches or defects that may not be visible under the microscope to prevent bipolar plate coating corrosion during the 100-h electrolysis. Even small failure in gold coating can cause further corrosion of steel beneath that forms a green solution that can be the oxidation and dissolution of chromium to Cr²⁺ and Cr³⁺ ions. This contaminates the electrolytes and the membrane by ion-exchanging protons to larger positive ions. The ion-exchange in the membrane has an impact on hydrogen mobility though the membrane and therefore in hydrogen production. The lessons learnt from this deliverable will be implemented in the upcoming months in preparation for the 100-hour run where the aim would be to run the experiments closer to the industrial pilot conditions while keeping in mind the safety limitations of the University and lab-based experiments.

6. References

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